

Analysis of The Effect of Talent Management on Employees' Intent to Leave^a

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Abstract

With the increasing importance of intellectual capital, the effective and efficient utilization of human potential within an organization has become a crucial competitive factor. Talent management, an advanced human resources practice that has gained significance in recent years in business organizations, focuses on the skills of employees. In this study, talent management practices aimed at selecting, employing, training, developing, and retaining talented candidates based on their skills in appropriate positions within the organization were examined, specifically in the banking sector. Hypotheses were formulated to investigate the impact of talent management practices in banks on employees' intention to leave. The data necessary to test the hypotheses were obtained through a survey applied to 421 bank employees in some provinces in Turkey. The survey results were analyzed using various statistical methods and testing techniques (frequency distribution, mean, T-test, ANOVA, correlation, and regression) by SPSS. A statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted in all analyses. As a result of the analysis, it was founded that talent management has a significant correlation with the intention to leave. Consequently, the findings indicate that the implementation of talent management reduces the intention to leave, and evaluations and comments are made within this framework.

Keywords: Talent, Talent Management, Intention to Leave, Turnover Intention

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's business world, where the impact of competition is felt in every field, it has been revealed that the most important competitive factor of organizations is human resources (Ulrich, 1996). Talented and qualified employees who are committed to their institution and job constitute desired workforce profile for all organizations. All business organizations want to see employees with these qualifications in their institutions and thus gain a competitive advantage that is not easy to imitate. The 'core competence' strategy, which reveals a significant difference in strategic management, can be summarized as business organizations having inimitable qualities and competencies and existing in the business world with this. Skilled and competent employees, which are the most important factors of these competencies, are more valuable to the organization than other resources.

The concept of talent management is a management concept that has emerged in recent years and reveals a specialized application form of 'strategic human resources management' in order to recruit, train and develop talented individuals into the organization and to keep these employees in the organization. Considering the importance of talented employees for the organization, as well as the fact that they are more selective about the work environment and conditions than other employees, the concept of talent management becomes more important for organizations (Sareen and Mishra, 2016; Ansar & Baloch, 2018).

1.1. Talent Management

In today's business world, the competitive advantage of organizational entities is closely linked to the abilities, competencies, and adaptability to change of their employees (Whitley, 2007). In an environment where the organizational workforce is perceived as a key element, the selection, training, and retention of qualified employees come to the forefront for organizational objectives. Organizations strive to invest in their employees, aiming to find individuals with suitable potential and talent to ensure that this investment is not in vain and yields returns. The efforts made by organizations underscore the significance of talent management practices. When definitions related to talents are examined in the academic literature, it is observed that the concept of talent is expressed by highlighting its various characteristics.

The concept of talent is defined as *the quality, ability, or aptitude of an individual to understand or accomplish something* (www.tdk.gov.tr). Talent is the capability of an individual to perform tasks more easily, enhance productivity, and mobilize those around them to achieve success within a specific period (Doğan & Demiral, 2008:150). According to Çırpan and Şen, talent can be described as individuals with superior qualities at a level that could play a role in the destiny of an organization, possessing the potential to fill managerial and technical positions with a promising future (Çırpan & Şen, 2009:110). In another definition, talent encompasses the entirety of a person's mental features, such as the ability to grasp specific relationships, analyze, solve problems, and reach conclusions, as well as certain physical characteristics (Erdoğan, 1999). While talent is an innate potential that accompanies an individual, particularly in a specific field, it can be defined as the systematic development and enhanced activity of this potential in a specific skill area (Gagne, 2013:2). Individuals with exceptional abilities (giftedness) have greater talents.

However, the concept of exceptional talent includes productivity and motivation (Renzulli, 1978). Talented employees must have skills, wills, and purposes; they must be capable, committed, and contributing (Ulrich & Smallwood, 2011:60). With these considerations, talent can be expressed as the innate, individual capacities that individuals utilize in organizing their perception, evaluation, actions, and behaviors, which develop through innate learning and application.

With the rise in the well-being of employees and the increasing importance of knowledge workers in contemporary business organizations, the expectations of employees are undergoing a transformation (Kelloway and Barling, 2000). Working in a meaningful, motivating, self-improvement-oriented, continuously learning, talent-compatible, work-life balanced, and justly distributed job is among the most crucial expectations of individuals today (Korkut, 2019). Furthermore, the desire to manage career development within a certain systematic framework is another significant expectation (Aksoy et al., 2016; Çırpan & Şen, 2009:112; Aslantaş, 2024). Retention of talent does not only mean of ensuring that a well qualified workforce is retained but it is also linked to how these talents can be nurtured and motivated to consistently strive for success and growth. The more employees' talents are managed and developed the more they are likely to focus their energies on improving their performance and focus their individual energy to the success of the organisation (Mpofu, 2012). In modern businesses, talented employees perceive themselves not merely as assets but as investors, expecting a return on investment from their organizations. In situations where their expectations are not met, these employees may easily leave the organization or, in cases of dissatisfaction, work with low productivity, resulting in poor performance that may lead to their own dismissal by managers, not voluntary departure (Doğan & Demiral, 2008:156). From this perspective, according to Ulrich and Smallwood (2011:57), talent means investing in the next generation.

The expectations of new talented employees are generally higher compared to other employees. While these expectations vary, it can be stated that they are looking for a work environment that is suitable for their talents and allows them to develop those talents. Simultaneously, they expect to be rewarded in proportion to the contributions they make to the organization (Gallardo-Gallardo, 2018; Ng et al. 2010). According to Freiberg and Freiberg, individuals aware of their talents do not base their job and workplace preferences solely on material conditions; rather, they blend their financial and emotional expectations when making decisions. These expectations are outlined below (Freiberg and Freiberg, 2005; cited in Altuntuğ, 2009):

- A work environment that considers the concepts of career and family together
- Assignment that is meaningful and can reveal talent
- Flexible working environment and hours
- Sincere and warm business friendship
- Management approach that enables and supports the sharing of information
- A work environment that includes hobbies and social relationships

The concepts of talent and talent management were brought to the forefront through McKinsey research in 1997. McKinsey, a U.S.-based management consulting firm, conducted research on talent with approximately 6,900 executives in 56 major American companies. The research revealed that despite these companies not experiencing growth-related issues in the past five years,

they faced challenges in terms of a competent workforce. The most significant issues reported by managers were identified as attracting talented individuals to the organization (at a rate of 89%) and retaining talented employees (at a rate of 90%). In the updated study in 2000, it was found that attracting talent had become more challenging compared to the findings in 1997 (Axelrod, Handfield-Jones & Welsh, 2001). Furthermore, according to the Talent Shortage research conducted by Manpower Inc. in 2006, which involved 33,000 employees in 23 countries, problems related to talented employees were identified (Atlı, 2013:59).

The concept of talent management involves a planned and structured approach by the organization, encompassing the recruitment, placement, and development stages of talented individuals, with the desire to employ individuals who consistently perform high (Akar, 2015:25). Stockey defines talent management as a conscious and planned approach to the execution of attracting, hiring, developing, and retaining actions in alignment with the organization's current and future needs, along with the skills and abilities of the workforce (Stockey, 2003). Viewing talent management as a process, Çırpan and Şen assert that it is a management process centered around the 'Human Resources,' systematically working to bridge the gap between the talents needed for coping with the challenges the company may face and achieving its goals by implementing strategies (Çırpan & Şen, 2009).

Taking these definitions into consideration, talent management can be expressed as a specialized advanced human resources practice that focuses on the employee, according to the understanding of talent. It involves identifying key positions, tasks, and activities required in the organization, attracting suitable talent for these positions, selecting, placing, orienting, training, and developing them, as well as motivating and retaining them. The execution of necessary planning and implementation efforts is integral to this talent-oriented approach.

Within this regard, for an effective implementation of talent management, organizations need to determine in advance the strategy they will adopt, along with the roadmap and methodology. Expectations related to talent management practices may vary within the framework of the organization's field of activity and needs.

All these statements emphasize the significance of the talent management process for organizations. Different researchers have proposed various models related to the talent management process. According to Ashton and Morton (2005:29), the talent management process consists of ten stages. These stages are:

- Revision of talent structures (a review of principles, job scope, and talent market trends),
- Positioning strategies (strategic or tactical decisions, planning actions and talent processes),
- Job-integrated talents (strategic management process, three-month/annual business plans, leadership, alignment of defined talent roles, and job quality),
- Talent-focused leadership approach,
- Talent and cultural alignment (common language, consistent messages, addressing cultural characteristics, and mitigating negative impacts),
- Establishment of an accountability culture (quality, understanding of accountability),

- Process design and implementation (human/technology issues, evaluation of talent processes and deficiencies, success rates, examination of talent development potential, achievement of talent performance),
- Evaluation of talent performance,
- Keeping talent management on the agenda,
- Review of talent management (deficiencies, comparison with other organizations).

According to another researcher, Cheese, to reveal the impact of talent management, there must be dynamic integration stages between talented employees and the organization. These stages can be expressed as discovering talent, developing talent, distributing talent, and aligning talents with business strategies (Cheese, 2008:30)

In another study (Tabançali & Korumaz, 2014), the talent management process is expressed as follows:

- Defining goals and strategies,
- Identifying key positions,
- Defining requirements suitable for the position,
- Creating a talent pool,
- Recruitment,
- Training and development,
- Performance evaluation, and
- Retention - building commitment.

Then, in order to achieve their organizational objectives through employees, organizations need to meet the needs of employees, implement practices that motivate them, and establish organizational commitment. Organizations that fail to motivate and establish commitment among their employees may find it challenging to succeed. While individuals have various needs, it is observed that the individual need for a career perspective where they can showcase their talents, believe they need to personally accomplish something, and make efforts towards it is crucial. Creating an appropriate and accessible career plan within the organization will enhance employee commitment and reduce the intention to leave the job.

1.2. Intent to Leave

In today's competitive business environment, where companies need to exert more effort to stay afloat, it can be asserted that talented employees with specific competencies and high organizational commitment are a valuable part of the business. The recruitment, orientation, skill development, motivation, and establishment of corporate loyalty for these employees form a significant aspect of intellectual capital (Ashton, 2005; Zhou & Fink, 2003). However, fulfillment of employees' needs and ensuring the consistent continuity of this situation are essential. The departure of a talented and qualified employee, on whom the organization has exerted such efforts and investment, will not only lead to significant financial losses but also result in intangible losses for the organization (Allen, 2012). This aspect should be taken into consideration by businesses.

The intention of employees to leave the organization has been a critical issue for organizational management for years, and it is still considered a significant problem area for organizations today (Rainayee, 2013:48). Organizations particularly desire qualified employees to continue working for them over the long term. This is because the departure of employees who socialize within the organization, exhibit organizational commitment, and demonstrate high performance is thought to lead to significant costs for the organization in terms of the investments made in the employees (recruitment, orientation, training, etc.) (Çelik & Çıra, 2013:11). Therefore, high employee turnover is acknowledged as a significant problem for organizations. The costs of new employees for the organization are high, and their work quality is lower (Fakunmoju et al., 2010:313). The departure of qualified and talented employees, who require significant effort, capital, and time for development in line with the organization's goals and objectives, becomes a significant cost factor for organizations (Üstün & Doğan, 2014:576).

The concept of turnover behavior and turnover intention are distinct in academic literature. Turnover behavior refers to an employee terminating their employment, whereas turnover intention signifies the employee's contemplation of terminating their employment before actually doing so. Broadly, turnover intention is described as an individual's intention to leave their current workplace. Specifically, it can be characterized as an individual's subjective estimate of the likelihood of leaving an organization in the near future (Cho et al., 2009:374). According to Kang, turnover intention is defined as the conscious probability of an employee leaving their current job in the near future and is considered a crucial determinant of turnover behavior (Kang et al., 2015). Rainayee posits that turnover intention is the organizational member's subjective feelings and cognitive intent regarding their current job and work environment in light of alternative opportunities (Rainayee, 2013:48). Yener describes turnover intention as the employee's deliberate and willing desire to leave their job (Yener, 2014:81).

Alternatively, turnover intention can be defined as a destructive and active action exhibited by employees when dissatisfied with their working conditions (Onay & Kılıcı, 2011:365). In summary, 'turnover intention' can be expressed as the reluctance of an individual to continue their organizational role in the future for organizational or external reasons (Aksoy et al., 2016), which has not yet materialized into an actual decision to leave. From another perspective, turnover intention is a tendency manifested in reduced job performance, weakened organizational commitment, and behaviors of incongruence with the work environment and other employees (Aslantaş, 2024). In essence, turnover intention represents an inclination to terminate current employment, signaling the initiation of a process leading towards transitioning to another job that the employee believes will fulfill their expectations.

The departure of highly skilled and qualified elite personnel with high performance is not a desirable situation for businesses. The intention of individuals to leave their jobs before actually leaving is a significant precursor to turnover behavior, and identifying and eliminating the reasons during the intention phase can guide businesses in employee retention (Ari et al., 2010:144). Generally, employees exhibit their intentions to leave their jobs through various behaviors before actual turnover. It is essential for managers to first identify the feasibility level of this intention along with its reasons, present solution options, and address the issue in order to guide businesses in acquiring and retaining personnel.

For every employee contemplating leaving their job, the factors giving rise to turnover intention may vary based on the employee's needs and expectations from the organization. However, upon examining various studies, it is observed that there are some common factors contributing to the formation of turnover intention. In the literature, the factors leading to voluntary turnover intention, initiated by the employee's own will, are evaluated as organizational and non-organizational factors (Gebremichael, 2019; An et al., 2022; Park & Min, 2020; Olya et al., 2022; Ozer & Aslantas, 2023). Various external factors (such as unemployment rate, alternative job opportunities, etc.), organizational factors (management style, job satisfaction, salary, rewards, workload, job dissatisfaction, etc.), and personal factors (gender, age, family, health, education, and cultural level, etc.) are seen to influence turnover intention.

Within the organizational environment, numerous events occur that positively or negatively impact employees. Positive situations, depending on the employee's perception, increase the intention to stay in the organization, while negative situations may trigger the intention to leave. According to Şahin, organizations resort to elements such as job design, incentives, and improvements in salaries to retain qualified workforce and enhance job satisfaction (Şahin, 2011:285). If motivational incentives are not adequately implemented by the organization, employees may contemplate evaluating alternative job options (Kingır et al., 2016).

Turnover intention is akin to a seed planted in the realm of thought. It germinates, grows, and develops as conditions mature. The growth and development of this thought lead to various negativities. These adversities, in a vicious cycle, nourish and amplify the intention. If the environment and conditions affecting the employee are not rectified, the employee may leave the organization. Even if an employee has an intention to leave the job for any reason, not acting on that intention may still result in detrimental effects for the organization due to the employee's negative attitude.

1.3. The Relationship Between Talent Management and Intention to Leave

Turnover intention is a significant precursor to the act of leaving a job, emerging as the desire of employees to terminate their employment due to job-related or non-job-related reasons. One influential factor contributing to the formation of employees' intention to leave is the evaluation of whether the tasks they perform align with their capabilities or not (Cardy & Selvarajan, 2006). When the job aligns with their abilities, employees are expected to achieve higher job satisfaction. Conversely, when the job does not match their abilities, it is assessed that it may lead to low morale and difficulties in work life. The exploration of the relationship between talent management and intention to leave seeks to unveil the strategies and practices organizations employ to attract, nurture, and retain their workforce. Talent management encompasses diverse dimensions such as recruitment, training, career development, and performance management. Understanding how talent management practices impact employees' intentions to leave is crucial for organizations striving to bolster employee retention and overall organizational effectiveness. (Rumawas, 2021; Al-Dalahmeh et al., 2020).

2. Methodology

2.1. Purpose and Significance of the Study

The aim of this research is to investigate the impact of talent management strategies employed by banks, particularly in a field where employee skills, such as in the banking sector, create significant difference and value concerning the quality of the produced services. The objective is to examine the influence of these talent management strategies on the factor of employees' intention to leave, thereby assessing the effectiveness of talent management in the industry.

While this topic has been partially explored in other application areas (Škerháková et al., 2022; Fahmi & Mohamed, 2020), there is a lack of sufficient research regarding the application and results in the banking sector. This study is anticipated to reveal important data regarding the influence of talent management on employees' intention to leave in the banking sector, fostering awareness, especially in the planning and implementation of talent management practices within the industry. Within this framework, the goal is to employ, train, develop, and plan careers for employees based on their talents. Consequently, this approach aims to enhance the quality of services produced, establish a healthy work environment, and generate awareness in the banking sector regarding the importance of considering talent-related factors in planning and implementation.

2.2. Research Hypotheses

The research question addressing this issue is formulated as follows: 'Is there a relationship between talent management and turnover intention?'

To uncover the relationship between talent management and its sub-dimensions with turnover intention, the following hypotheses will be tested:

H1: There is a significant relationship between talent management and the intention to leave the job.

H1a: There is a significant relationship between the sub-dimension of Self talent assessment of talent management and the intention to leave the job.

H1b: There is a significant relationship between the sub-dimension of career talent assessment of talent management and the intention to leave the job.

H1c: There is a significant relationship between the sub-dimension of organizational talent assessment of talent management and the intention to leave the job.

2.3. Scope and Sample

The population of the study consists of employees working in public banks in Diyarbakır, Şanlıurfa, Mardin, Gaziantep, and Batman provinces of Turkey. A total of 550 surveys were randomly distributed to bank employees in these provinces. Out of these surveys, 442 were successfully collected. Among them, 21 surveys were marked in a way that rendered them ineligible for evaluation and were consequently excluded. As a result, 421 surveys were considered for analysis

2.4. Research Methodology and Measurement Instrument

The data collection phase of the research employed a questionnaire consisting of two sections. The demographic variables section of the questionnaire included items such as gender, age, marital

status, educational background, title, and years of service. The second section of the questionnaire comprised the talent management scale and turnover intention scale.

In the classification of the scales, a 5-point Likert scale was used, with $n=5$, and the value of $n-1/n=0.8$ was determined. Additionally, the following value range was utilized for making general interpretations about the scale-related data:

- 1.00 < $n \leq 1.80$ Range: Very Low
- 1.81 < $n \leq 2.60$ Range: Low
- 2.61 < $n \leq 3.40$ Range: Moderate
- 3.41 < $n \leq 4.20$ Range: High
- 4.21 < $n \leq 5.00$ Range: Very High

Factor and item averages have been interpreted and discussed in accordance with the classifications mentioned above.

Table 1. Value Ranges for 5-Point Likert Type Preferences

Weight	Options	Bounds	Classification
1	Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.80	Low
2	Disagree	1.81 – 2.60	Low
3	Partially Agree	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
4	Agree	3.41 – 4.20	High
5	Strongly Agree	4.21 – 5.00	Very High

The correspondences of the marked items based on preference weights are provided in the table.

2.4.1. Talent Management Scale

The Talent Management Scale was formed by incorporating certain items taken from a scale developed by Tutar et al. (2011), along with additional items added through literature review and expert opinions. Factor Analysis and Reliability Coefficient of Talent Management Scale Items were analyzed. It is seen that the scale consists of 3 dimensions. These dimensions are *Self Talent Assessment*, *Career Talent Assessment* and *Organizational Talent Assessment*. The reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) of all items of the talent management scale, which consists of 18 items in total, was found to be 0.942. While naming the dimensions of talent management, the following evaluations were taken as basis.

Self-Talent Assessment: This dimension represents an individual process where employees evaluate their tasks based on their own skills and competencies.

Career Talent Assessment: This dimension refers to organisational processes that support employees in determining their individual development and future career goals based on their existing talents.

Organizational Talent Assessment: This dimension evaluates, from the employees' perspective, the organization's attitude towards talented employees and its practices in talent assessment.

2.4.2. Turnover Intention Scale

The fourth scale of the questionnaire, the 'Turnover Intention Scale,' was adapted for the study by taking three items from a scale used in the doctoral thesis of Büyükbeşe (2012), which was originally derived from Reychav and Weisberg (2009) and consists of five items with a reliability coefficient of (Cronbach's alpha) 0.93. Alongside these items, an additional 5 items were created through literature review and expert input, resulting in an 8-item scale. The scale was subjected to factor analysis and reliability analysis. The Turnover Intention Scale items, factor analysis results and reliability coefficient (Cronbach alpha) value were measured as 0.89.

2.5. Data Analysis

In this study, the survey research method was employed. A total of 421 evaluations from employees were gathered through a constructed survey, and various statistical methods and test techniques (frequency distribution, mean, t-test, ANOVA, correlation, and regression) were utilized for analysis using SPSS v18.0. A statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered in the analysis. To determine whether parametric or non-parametric tests would be applied on the survey data, a normality test was conducted. As the Skewness-Kurtosis values of turnover intention and ability scales fell within the range of (-1.96; +1.96), indicating a normal distribution, the decision was made to apply parametric tests. The analysis of the data was conducted based on the total scores of participants' responses to the scale items.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings obtained through the analyses conducted in the study.

3.1. Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

The section on participants' demographic characteristics includes tables and evaluations specifying the gender, age, marital status, educational background, position in the organization, and years of service of the employees participating in the study.

3.1.1. Distribution According to Participants' Genders

The distribution of participants by gender is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Table of Participant Distribution According to Gender

Gender	N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)	Percentage
Male	204	48,5	48,5	
Female	217	51,5	100	

Total	421	100
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When examining the distribution of bank employees participating in the study according to gender, as presented in Table 2, it was determined that 48.5% of the employees (204 individuals) were male, while 51.5% (217 individuals) were female.

3.1.2. Distribution According to Age Groups of Participants

The distribution of participants according to age groups is illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. The Table of Distributions According to Age Groups of Participants

Age	N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
21-30	218	51,8	51,8
31-40	150	35,6	87,4
41-50	52	12,4	99,8
51-60	1	0,2	100
Total	421	100	

When Table 3 is examined, it is determined that the distribution of bank employees participating in the research according to age groups is as follows: 51.8% (218 individuals) in the 21-30 age range, 35.6% (150 individuals) in the 31-40 age range, 12.4% (52 individuals) in the 41-50 age range, and 0.2% (1 individual) in the 51-60 age range. There are 218 employees in the 21-30 age group and 150 employees in the 31-40 age group

3.1.3. Distribution According to Marital Status of Participants

The distribution according to the marital status of the participants is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. The Table of Distributions According to Marital Status of Participants

Marital Status	N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Married	280	66,5	66,5
Single	141	33,5	100
Total	421	100	

Upon examining the distribution according to marital status of bank employees, as indicated in Table 4, it was found that 66.5% of the employees (280 individuals) are married, while 33.5% (141 individuals) are single.

3.1.4. Distribution According to Educational Levels of Participants

The distribution according to the educational levels of the participants is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. The Table of Distributions According to Educational Levels of Participants

Educational Status	N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
High School	38	9	9
Associate Degree	18	4,3	13,3
Bachelor's Degree	311	73,9	87,2
Postgraduate	54	12,8	100
Total	421	100	

Upon examining the distribution according to educational levels of bank employees participating in the research, as indicated in Table 5, it was found that 9% of the employees (38 individuals) have completed high school, 4.3% (18 individuals) have completed an associate degree, 73.9% (311 individuals) have completed a bachelor's degree, and 12.8% (54 individuals) have completed postgraduate education. It is observed that the total percentage of those with high school and associate degree education is 13.3%.

3.1.5. Distribution According to Titles of Participants

The distribution according to the titles of the participants is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. The Table of Distributions According to Titles of Participants

Title	Number	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Bank Assistant	54	12,8	12,8
Service Representative	17	27,8	40,6
Service Supervisor	97	23	63,7
Specialist Assistant	5	1,2	64,8
Specialist	8	1,9	66,7
Assistant Director	70	16,6	83,4
Director	49	11,6	95
Branch Manager	21	5	100
Total	421	100	

Upon examining the distribution according to the titles of bank employees, as indicated in Table 6, it was found that 12.8% of the employees (54 individuals) hold the title of bank assistant, 27.8% (17 individuals) are service representatives, 23% (97 individuals) are service supervisors, 1.2% (5 individuals) are specialist assistants, 1.9% (8 individuals) are specialists, 16.6% (70 individuals) are assistant directors, 11.6% (49 individuals) are directors, and 5% (21 individuals)

are branch managers. The titles mentioned here are based on the positions in Ziraat Bank, while titles in Halk Bank and Vakıflar Bank may differ, they have been categorized accordingly for the purpose of this classification.

3.1.6. Distribution According to Years of Service of Participants

The distribution according to the years of service of the participants is illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7. The Distributions According to Years of Service of Participants

Years of Service	N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
0-5 year	202	48	48
6-10 year	135	32,1	80
11-15 year	10	2,4	82,4
16-20 year	63	15	97,4
21-25 year	11	2,6	100
Total	421	100	

When examined according to the years of service, as shown in Table 7, it is determined that 48% of the bank employees participating in the research (202 individuals) have 0-5 years of service, 32.1% (135 individuals) have 6-10 years, 2.4% (10 individuals) have 11-15 years, 15% (63 individuals) have 16-20 years, and 2.6% (11 individuals) have 21-25 years of service.

3.2. Statistical Findings on Talent Management Scale

The talent management scale consists of self-assessment, career assessment, and organizational assessment dimensions. In this section, descriptive statistical analyses will be conducted for the items that encompass these dimensions.

3.2.1. Statistical Findings on the Sub-Dimensions of Self-Talent Assessment in Talent Management

The items related to the self-assessment dimension of the talent management scale and preference statistics are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Statistical Distribution Table for Items Related to the Sub-Dimension of Self-Talent Assessment

Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean

	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
1. I believe that the work I do is suitable for my abilities.	16	3,8	22	5,2	86	20,4	160	38,0	137	32,5	3,90
2. I believe that I use my talents to their full capacity in a way that is suitable for the work I do.	7	1,7	33	7,8	101	24,0	156	37,1	124	29,5	3,80
3. I am serving in my department based on my experiences and professional qualifications.	19	4,5	50	11,9	78	18,5	159	37,8	115	27,3	3,71
4. I am serving in my department based on my personal characteristics.	39	9,3	68	16,2	96	22,8	134	31,8	84	20,0	3,37
5. I possess expertise at the level required for the skills needed for the job I perform.	7	1,7	30	7,1	93	22,1	172	40,9	119	28,3	3,86
6. I believe that my managers make sufficient use of my talents.	18	4,3	41	9,7	126	29,9	164	39,0	72	17,1	3,54

1- When the responses to the statement "I believe that the work I do is suitable for my abilities" were examined, it was observed that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 90.9%, and the item average was agree (3.90).

2- When the responses to the statement "I believe that I use my talents to their full capacity in a way that is suitable for the work I do" were examined, it was found that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 90.6%, and the item average was agree (3.80).

3- When the responses to the statement "I am serving in my department based on my experiences and professional qualifications" were examined, it was noted that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 83.6%, and the item average was agree (3.71).

4- When the responses to the statement "I am serving in my department based on my personal characteristics" were examined, it was observed that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 51.8%, and the item average was partially agree (3.37).

5- When the responses to the statement "I possess expertise at the level required for the skills needed for the job I perform" were examined, it was found that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 91.3%, and the item average was agree (3.86).

6- When the responses to the statement "I believe that my managers make sufficient use of my talents" were examined, it was noted that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 56.1%, and the item average was agree (3.56).

3.2.2. Statistical Findings on the Sub-Dimensions of Career Talent Assessment in Talent Management

The items related to the career assessment dimension of the talent management scale and preference statistics are provided in Table 9.

Table 9. Statistical Distribution Table for Items Related to the Sub-Dimension of Career Talent Assessment

Items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
1. My managers provide new opportunities for my professional development.	25	5,9	39	9,3	101	24,0	148	35,2	108	25,7	3,36
2. My managers provide sufficient support for my personal development.	26	6,2	39	9,3	90	21,4	164	39,0	102	24,2	3,65
3. My managers assist me in career planning related to my talents.	31	7,4	42	10,0	97	23,0	153	36,3	98	23,3	3,58
4. I believe that my managers have fully discovered the talents I have for the work I do.	25	5,9	82	19,5	147	34,9	105	24,9	62	14,7	3,23
5. Effective leadership is provided to talented employees in the organization where I work.	37	8,8	83	19,7	114	27,1	116	27,6	71	16,9	3,23

1- When the responses to the statement "My managers provide new opportunities for my professional development" were examined, it was observed that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 60.9%, and the item average was partially agree (3.36).

2- When the responses to the statement "My managers provide sufficient support for my personal development" were examined, it was found that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 84.6%, and the item average was agree (3.65).

3- When the responses to the statement "My managers assist me in career planning related to my talents" were examined, it was noted that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 82.6%, and the item average was agree (3.58).

4- When the responses to the statement "I believe that my managers have fully discovered the talents I have for the work I do" were examined, it was observed that the total of partially agree and strongly agree options was 74.5%, and the item average was partially agree (3.23).

5- When the responses to the statement "Effective leadership is provided to talented employees in the organization where I work" were examined, it was found that the total of partially agree, agree, and strongly agree options was 71.6%, and the item average was partially agree (3.23)..

3.2.3. Statistical Findings on the Sub-Dimensions of Organizational Talent Assessment in Talent Management

The items and preference statistics related to the organizational assessment dimension of the talent management scale are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Statistical Distribution Table for Items Related to the Sub-Dimension of Organizational Talent Assessment

Items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
1. Job rotation is implemented for talented employees in the organization where I work.	53	12,6	71	16,9	114	27,1	131	31,1	52	12,4	3,13
2. Future-oriented potential performance evaluations are conducted for talented employees in the organization where I work.	38	9,0	76	18,1	119	28,3	145	34,4	43	10,2	3,18
3. A strategy to attract competent minds is implemented in the organization where I work.	49	11,6	97	23,0	116	27,6	124	29,5	35	8,3	2,99
4. My managers provide mentorship (career counseling) to talented employees.	48	11,4	90	21,4	132	31,4	101	24,0	50	11,9	3,03
5. My managers select the most talented employee for positions.	54	12,8	59	14,0	147	34,9	106	25,2	55	13,1	3,11
6. My managers ensure strong coordination among talented employees.	36	8,6	69	16,4	135	32,1	129	30,6	52	12,4	3,21
7. My managers stimulate my interest in the work I do.	33	7,8	64	15,2	136	32,3	125	29,7	63	15,0	3,28

1- When the responses to the statement "Job rotation is implemented for talented employees in the organization where I work" were examined, it was observed that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 43.5%, and the item average was partially agree (3.13). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 56.6%.

2- When the responses to the statement "Future-oriented potential performance evaluations are conducted for talented employees in the organization where I work" were examined, it was found that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 44.6%, and the item average was partially agree (3.18). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 55.4%.

3- When the responses to the statement "A strategy to attract competent minds is implemented in the organization where I work" were examined, it was noted that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 37.8%, and the item average was partially agree (2.99). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 62.2%.

4- When the responses to the statement "My managers provide mentorship (career counseling) to talented employees" were examined, it was observed that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 35.9%, and the item average was partially agree (3.03). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 64.2%.

5- When the responses to the statement "My managers select the most talented employee for positions" were examined, it was found that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 38.3%, and the item average was partially agree (3.11). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 61.7%.

6- When the responses to the statement "My managers ensure strong coordination among talented employees" were examined, it was observed that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 33%, and the item average was partially agree (3.21). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 77%.

7- When the responses to the statement "My managers stimulate my interest in the work I do" were examined, it was found that the total of agree and strongly agree options was 44.7%, and the item average was partially agree (3.28). The total of strongly disagree, disagree, and partially agree options was 55.3%.

3.3. Statistical Findings on the Turnover Intention Scale

The items and preference statistics related to the turnover intention scale are provided in Table 11.

Table 11. Statistical Distribution Table for Items Related to the Turnover Intention Scale

Items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
1. I may leave my current job if I find a more suitable position for my skills.	81	19	104	25	91	22	70	17	75	18	2,89
2. I am considering leaving the job due to management-related issues.	177	42	141	34	60	14	29	6,9	14	3,3	1,96

3. I am contemplating leaving the job due to the nature of the work I do.	167	40	149	35	48	11	34	8,1	23	5,5	2,04
4. I am thinking of leaving the job due to personal issues.	207	49	156	37	22	5,2	17	4	19	4,5	1,78
5. I often contemplate quitting my job in this organization.	182	43	124	30	62	15	24	5,7	29	6,9	2,04
6. I am actively considering leaving this organization and actively looking for a new job.	205	49	140	33	36	8,6	20	4,8	20	4,8	1,84
7. If I had another job opportunity, I would leave my current job.	149	35	110	26	68	16	40	9,5	54	13	2,38
8. It is highly likely that I will actively search for a new job next year	211	50	125	30	35	8,3	21	5	29	6,9	1,89

1- Regarding the statement 'I may leave my current job if I find a more suitable position for my skills,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree, disagree, and somewhat agree options is 66%, with an average rating of somewhat agree (2.89).

2- For the statement 'I am considering leaving the job due to management-related issues,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree, disagree, and somewhat agree options is 90%, with an average rating of disagree (1.96).

3- Concerning the statement 'I am contemplating leaving the job due to the nature of the work I do,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree and disagree options is 86%, with an average rating of disagree (2.04).

4- Regarding the statement 'I am thinking of leaving the job due to personal issues,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree and disagree options is 91.2%, with an average rating of strongly disagree (1.78).

5- For the statement 'I often contemplate quitting my job in this organization,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree and disagree options is 88%, with an average rating of disagree (2.04).

6- Concerning the statement 'I am actively considering leaving this organization and actively looking for a new job,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree and disagree options is 90.6%, with an average rating of disagree (1.84).

7- Regarding the statement 'If I had another job opportunity, I would leave my current job,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree, disagree, and somewhat agree options is 77%, with an average rating of disagree (2.38).

8- Concerning the statement 'It is highly likely that I will actively search for a new job next year,' when examining the marked preferences, the total of strongly disagree and disagree options is 88.3%, with an average rating of disagree (1.89).

3.4. Relationship (Correlation) Analyses

The correlation table of talent management and its sub-dimensions, namely self-talent sub-dimension, career talent sub-dimension, and organizational talent sub-dimension with turnover intention is presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Correlation Table

	Talent Management	Intention to Leave Employment
Talent Management	1	
Intention to Leave Employment	-0,399**	1
Self-Talent Subdimension	0,790**	-0,315**
Career Talent Subdimension	0,916**	-0,364**
Organizational Talent Subdimension	0,925**	-0,371**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

When examining the relationship (correlation) analyses presented in Table 12, the following were found out:

There is a negative, linear, and moderately strong relationship ($r = -0.39$) between 'Talent Management' and 'Intention to Leave,' and this relationship is significant ($p < 0.01$). **Hypothesis H1 is confirmed.**

There is a negative, linear, and moderately strong relationship ($r = -0.31$) between the subdimension 'Self-Talent' of Talent Management and 'Intention to Leave,' and this relationship is significant ($p < 0.01$). **Hypothesis H1a is confirmed.**

There is a negative, linear, and moderately strong relationship ($r = -0.36$) between the subdimension 'Career Talent' of Talent Management and 'Intention to Leave,' and this relationship is significant ($p < 0.01$). **Hypothesis H1b is confirmed.**

There is a negative, linear, and moderately strong relationship ($r = -0.37$) between the subdimension 'Organizational Talent' of Talent Management and 'Intention to Leave,' and this relationship is significant ($p < 0.01$). **Hypothesis H1c is confirmed.**

3.5. Effect (Regression) Analyses on the Intention to Leave and Talent Management

The impact analysis on the intention to leave and behavioral aspects of talent management sub-dimensions, namely Self-Talent, career talent, and organizational talent, is presented in Table 13 and Table 14.

Table 13. Table of Impact Analysis on Intention to Leave and Talent Management

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Estimated Standard Error
1	0,399 ^a	0,159	0,153	0,83097

a. Influencers: Self-Talent, Organizational Talent, Career Talent

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Square of the Mean	F	P
1	Regression	54,563	3	18,188	26,340	0,000 ^a
	Residual	287,940	417	0,691		
	Total	342,503	420			

a. Influencers: Organizational Talent, Self-Talent, Career Talent

b. Dependent Variable: Intention to Leave the Job

The multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of 'talent management' on 'intention to leave the job' (Table 13) was explored at a significance level of 0.01, indicating 99% confidence. The regression analysis revealed that at the $p < 0.01$ significance level, job dedication behavior was influenced by talent management in a linear and negative direction at a rate of 0.153 (15.3%) ($R = 0.399$, $R^2 = 0.159$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.153$; $F = 26.340$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 14. The Impact Analysis (Regression) Table of Intention to Leave the Job and Talent Management Sub-Dimensions

Coefficients^a

Independent Variables	B	Std. Error	Adjusted Beta	t	P
(Constant)	3,645	0,208		17,556	0,000
1 Self-Talent	-0,151	0,070	-0,124	-2,154	0,032
Career Talent	-0,118	0,072	-0,130	-1,635	0,103
Organizational Talent	-0,183	0,070	-0,197	-2,606	0,009

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to Leave

To examine the effects of talent management dimensions on the intention to leave the job, a multiple linear regression analysis was conducted (Table 14). The impact of self-talent, career talent, and corporate talent dimensions on the intention to leave the job is investigated. The results of the regression analysis indicate that at the significance level of $p < 0.01$, the "Self-Talent"

dimension of talent management has a linear and negative effect of 0.151 (15.1%), and at the significance level of $p < 0.05$, the "Organizational talent" dimension of talent management has a linear and negative effect of 0.183 (18.3%) on the intention to leave the job. It can be stated that the "career talent" dimension of talent management either has no significant effect or has a very low level of influence ($p > 0.05$).

The determined R² values in the regression analysis show the extent to which the talent management dimensions in the research model affect the intention to leave the job. The R² value is determined as 15.3%. This value indicates that the talent management dimensions influence the dedication behavior to the job by 15.3%, and this influence is in a negative direction.

When the effect values are substituted into the regression formulation $Y = a + bX$ as follows:

Intention to Leave the Job = 3,645 - 0.151 $X_{self-talent}$ - 0.118 $X_{career\ talent}$ - 0.183 $X_{organizational\ talent}$ + ϵ
can be expressed.

The results of the regression analysis indicate that talent management negatively affects intent to leave.

3.6. ANOVA Analyses

Talent management and its sub-dimensions, namely self-talent, career talent, and organizational talent, were analyzed to determine whether there are differences in turnover intention based on demographic characteristics using t-tests and ANOVA analyses. Only significant differences are reported in the findings.

3.6.1. Findings Based on Age Variable

The significant values obtained from the ANOVA analyses conducted based on the participants' age variables are shown in Table 15.

Table 15. ANOVA Table for Age Variable

Age-Related Variable	Age		Sum of Squares	Mean Difference	F	p
Talent Management	21-30	31-40	267,7	-0,22714*	4,56	0,004
		41-50		-0,33994*		
Self-Talent dimension	Sub-21-30	31-40	232,1	-0,38381*	12,95	0,000
		41-50		-0,50731*		
Intention to Leave	41-50	21-30	342,5	-0,39054*	2,823	0,039
		31-40		-0,36613*		

As seen in Table 15, a significant difference at a 95% confidence level regarding "talent management" based on participants' age variable was tested. The analysis revealed a significant difference at a 95% confidence level or 0.05 significance level regarding "talent management" based on age variable ($F=4.56$; $p<0.05$). This difference was subjected to Post Hoc Scheffe analysis to determine its direction. According to the analysis, there was a favor towards participants aged between 31-40 and 41-50, while participants aged between 21-30 showed a disadvantage.

Participants' age variable was also tested for significant differences in the "Self-Talent sub-dimension," a sub-dimension of talent management, at a 95% confidence level. The analysis revealed a significant difference at a 99% confidence level or 0.01 significance level regarding the "innate talent sub-dimension" based on age variable ($F=12.95$; $p<0.01$). Similarly, Post Hoc Scheffe analysis indicated a favor towards participants aged between 31-40 and 41-50, while those aged between 21-30 showed a disadvantage.

Furthermore, participants' age variable was examined for significant differences in "intention to leave the job" at a 95% confidence level. The analysis revealed a significant difference at a 95% confidence level or 0.05 significance level regarding "intention to leave the job" based on age variable ($F=2.823$; $p<0.05$). According to Post Hoc Scheffe analysis, there was a favor towards participants aged between 21-30 and 31-40, while those aged between 41-50 showed a disadvantage.

3.6.2. Findings Based on Educational Status Variable

The significant values found for the ANOVA analyses conducted based on participants' educational levels are shown in Table 16.

Table 16. ANOVA Table for Educational Level Variable

Educational Level Variable	Education Level	Sum of Squares	Mean Difference	F	p
Intention to leave	High School		0,03643		
	Associate's Degree	342,5	0,40741	4,6	0,004
	Bachelor's Degree		0,40482*		

Participants were examined for significant differences in "intention to leave" based on their educational level with 95% confidence. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "intention to leave" according to the educational level variable at a significance level of 0.05 or 95% confidence ($F=4.6$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis was conducted to determine who benefited from this difference. The analysis found a preference towards postgraduate graduates and a disadvantage for undergraduate graduates.

3.6.3. Findings According to Job Title Variable

The significant values found for the ANOVA analyses conducted according to the participants' job title variables are shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Job Title Variable ANOVA Table

Dependent Variable by Job Title	Job Title		Sum of Squares	Mean Difference	F	p
Talent Management	Service Representative	Director	267,69	-,52060*	3,47	0,001
		Branch Manager		-,58031*		
		Service Supervisor		-,44273**		
Self-Talent Sub-dimension	Bank Assistant	Director	232,1	-0,68594	7,41	0,000
		Branch Manager		-,83333*		
		Service Representative		-,71780*		
Intention to leave	to Branch Manager	Service Supervisor	342,5	-,68182*	3,72	0,001
		Specialist Assistant		-1,45476*		
		Assistant Director		-,78512*		

Participants were tested for significant differences in "talent management" based on their job titles at the institution, with a 95% confidence level. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "talent management" based on job titles ($F=3.47$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis indicated that directors and branch managers were favored in terms of talent management, while service clerks were at a disadvantage.

Participants were also tested for significant differences in the "self-talent management" sub-dimension based on their job titles at the institution, with a 95% confidence level. The analysis revealed a significant difference in the "Self-Talent management" sub-dimension based on job titles ($F=7.41$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis indicated that service supervisors and branch managers were favored in terms of self-talent management, while bank assistants were at a disadvantage.

Moreover, participants were tested for significant differences in "intention to leave the job" based on their job titles at the institution, with a 95% confidence level. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "intention to leave the job" based on job titles ($F=3.72$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis indicated that Service Representative, service supervisors, assistant specialists, and Assistant Director were favored in terms of intention to leave the job, while branch managers were at a disadvantage.

3.6.4. Findings Based on Years of Service Variable

Significant values obtained from the ANOVA analyses conducted based on the participants' years of service variable are presented in Table 18.

Table 18. ANOVA Table for Years of Service Variable

Variable	Dependent on	Years of Service	Sum of Squares	of Mean Difference	F	p
Talent Management	0-5 year	6-10 year	267,7	-0,1562	5,71	0,001
		11-15 year		-0,1815		
		16-20 year		-0,43827*		
Self-Talent dimension	0-5 year	6-10 year	232,05	-0,25061*	16,56	0,000
		11-15 year		-0,2617		
		16-20 year		-0,66847*		
Intention to leave	16-20 year	0-5 year	342,5	-0,32180*	4,23	0,006
		6-10 year		-0,45793*		
		11-15 year		-0,2686		

Participants' tenure in the organization was analyzed for its significance in terms of "talent management" at a confidence level of 95%. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "talent management" based on tenure, with a significance level of 0.05 or 95% confidence ($F=5.71$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis was conducted to determine in whose favor the difference lay. The analysis indicated that in terms of talent management, there was a difference favoring employees with 16-20 years of tenure over those with 0-5 years.

Participants' tenure in the organization was also examined for its significance in terms of the sub-dimension of "self-talent management" at a confidence level of 95%. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "self-talent management" based on tenure, with a significance level of 0.01 or 99% confidence ($F=16.56$; $p<0.01$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis was conducted to determine in whose favor the difference lay. The analysis indicated that in terms of self-talent management, there was a difference favoring employees with 6-10 years and 16-20 years of tenure over those with 0-5 years.

Furthermore, participants' tenure in the organization was analyzed for its significance in terms of "intention to leave" at a confidence level of 95%. The analysis revealed a significant difference in "intention to leave" based on tenure, with a significance level of 0.05 or 95% confidence ($F=4.23$; $p<0.05$). Post Hoc Scheffe analysis was conducted to determine in whose favor the difference lay. The analysis indicated that in terms of intention to leave, there was a difference favoring employees with 0-5 years and 6-10 years of tenure over those with 16-20 years.

RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The banking sector requires high performance and dynamic customer relationships as a benchmark. Therefore, bank employees are expected to be dynamic and high-performing, often

leading to a preference for younger employees. The dynamism and performance of young employees are advantageous for banks.

Bank employees generally perceive that they are suitable for their roles due to their skills and take on responsibilities based on their experiences and professional qualifications. Although they may attribute their involvement to personal traits, they actually express that professional competence is more crucial and thus engage accordingly. This may stem from the belief among employees that their personal qualities and professional skills are aligned with their job roles, and they are competent at an expert level. However, there may also be employees who have a lower level of agreement with this perspective.

According to the findings, employees generally perceive that their managers recognize their talents and assess them appropriately for tasks that match their abilities. However, some feel that their managers fail to discover their talents at the desired level, resulting in underutilization of their capabilities. This indicates the need for bank managers to address the issue.

Overall, 60% of employees believe that their managers provide new opportunities for professional development. However, a 40% segment holds negative views on this matter. It is expected that bank management reviews its efforts and provides employees with new professional opportunities. It can be stated that managers demonstrate a high level of support for employees' personal development and provide assistance in career planning. Additionally, it is observed that bank managers make significant efforts in effective leadership for talented employees. This underscores that banks are organizations that are open to innovation and invest in human resources. However, it should be noted that there are employees with negative perceptions, indicating the need for the improvement of practices in this regard.

Employees appear to have partly positive attitudes towards job rotation for talented employees, partly positive attitudes towards conducting future-oriented potential performance evaluations, and partly positive attitudes towards mentoring for talented employees. Considering the existence of different attitudes amongst employees, it can be stated that bank managements need to make improvement efforts in these areas.

Employees seem to have partly positive views on the strategy to attracting competent minds regarding their organizations, partly positive views on managers selecting the most talented individuals for suitable positions, and partly positive views on managers facilitating coordination among talented employees. Taking these findings into account, it can be expressed that bank managements should exert more effort in attracting and retaining talented and competent employees, making appropriate selections for positions, and facilitating coordination among employees.

It is observed that the awareness of talent among the younger generation is insufficient, and this awareness increases with age. It can be argued that individuals exhibit behavior stemming from not fully recognizing their talents at an early age. Due to concerns about finding employment and fear of losing current jobs, young individuals tend to push their talents into the background, only to realize these talents later in life. Any of these reasons can trigger the desire to discover talents as an internal necessity as individuals age. The situation of talents being revealed and expressed

in different ways can lead to discomfort or dissatisfaction if this need is not fulfilled. In this context, it is observed that demands for talents become more pronounced in older ages. Consequently, it can be expressed that the emergence of individual talent is dependent on experience.

It is believed that talent management is intricately linked to increasing job satisfaction and reducing turnover intentions among employees by enabling them to work in roles that align with their talents. The detrimental impact of turnover intentions on organizations further underscores the importance of talent management. The findings from this research reveal that talent management reduces turnover intentions, a result supported by other studies (Mpofu, 2012; Rumawas, 2021). Also according to Akbaş' research, investments in talents have been found to increase employees' desire to stay within the organization (Akbaş, 2013). Tümen's study demonstrates that proper implementation of talent management reduces turnover intentions and increases organizational commitment (Tümen, 2014). However, it can be argued that employees, in general, are partially willing to leave their current positions if they perceive that their current roles do not fully utilize their talents and if there are other job opportunities that better align with their talents. Altuntuğ suggests that in cases where talents discovered and developed within the organization fail to foster organizational loyalty, employees may readily transition to other enterprises, taking their talents with them (Altuntuğ, 2009:458). In this context, it is crucial to undertake efforts aimed at enhancing the organizational commitment of talented employees.

As the level of education increases, employees' expectations tend to rise (Aslantaş & Er, 2016). Employees who cannot find the desired environment within their current organization often consider alternative job offers, leading to the emergence of turnover intentions. To meet the organization's needs arising from these expectations, the organization must provide alternative job opportunities based on career progression. The need to develop business policies to meet the material and non-material needs of employees according to their level of education becomes more apparent.

It can be stated that employees do not have serious issues with management, and even if they do, these issues are insignificant enough not to affect their intention to leave the job. Additionally, it can be noted that employees who do not have problems with their work do not have intentions to leave their jobs. Employees who do not wish to leave their jobs, even if there are other job opportunities available, can be said to have high job satisfaction. As the years of employment increase, it can be expressed that employees who have been working in the organization for a long time have lower intentions to leave their jobs, are less willing to change jobs, and have no effective reason to change their working conditions. It can be stated that new employees have different expectations and may therefore be more daring in terms of leaving their jobs. Further studies in this area will enable the exploration of different aspects of the issue.

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